

IN SITU MONITORING OF LIQUID COMPOSITE PROCESSING

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1 Introduction

In situ process monitoring techniques are numerous and still seldom used in composite industry. They are however the only way to ensure reproductive and optimal performances of composite materials.

A comparison of different existing techniques will be presented and taking in account the different needs existing between laboratories and industrials. Physical parameters of a processing cycle will be reviewed. A special focus will be made on non intrusive heat flux measurements [1]. Correlations between real-time measurements and physical states properties (Cure level, Glass transition temperature and Mechanical properties) will be presented in order to describe a general approach.

2 Background

2.1 Monitoring methods

By screening the different existing physical properties (mechanical, thermal, electrical, optical...), it is possible to identify several interesting methods for composite processing monitoring. A brief comparison between possibilities and existing commercial solution is performed.

TFX-183 active sensor for non intrusive infusion monitoring.

2.2 Process constrains

Considering user's needs lead to different constrains concerning available solutions. Among them, the intrusiveness, precision, complexity and cost have to be taken in account.

2.3 Validations

Almost all applicable process monitoring methods provide indirect measurements which need to be calibrated according to actual properties.

For instance degree of cure α which is a chemical property is generally determined indirectly by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) in order to measure remaining curing heat associated to reactive species. The link between reactive heat flux F and conversion level α is given by a differential equation involving global reaction enthalpy ΔH :

$$F = \Delta H \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (1)$$

In production environment, a relative approach is generally sufficient considering the proportionality between cure rate and heat flux.

In laboratory, it is often necessary to cross different results and perform careful calibrations before any publication.

In the same way, electrical resistance of resin or time of flight of Ultrasonic Waves are linked through temperature to resin viscosity, cure level and Glass transition temperature (via DiBenedeto equation). In all cases an initial calibration is to be performed in order to achieve exploitable in situ measurements.

2.4 Multiphysics validations

Performing multiple measurements on the same experiment permits to identify multiple characteristics of material changes according to time and minimize the risk of error due to processing conditions. *HFC-200* is a special tool [2,3]

developed by *Metravib* and *TFX* which provides in the same experiment Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (*DMA*), Chemical and Thermal Shrinkage and Calorimetry according to time on Coin-Sized sample processed in situ.

HFC-200 cell to be mounted on a DMA

Multi-physics analysis is perfect for thermo-mechanical and kinetics modeling, but also for in situ methods calibration.

3 Experiments, results

A typical experimental approach is presented with different in situ monitoring techniques and pending experimental validation (*DSC*, *DMA*, *HFC-200*).

A special focus will concern in situ resin flow characterization with intrusive and non intrusive measurements performed at the same time. The different available techniques allow to detect flow front, flow velocity, and characterize resin state during flow. Since processing also involve 3D flows, identification of flow in z-direction is also investigated.

Cure often starts during resin flow stage. This is one good reason for having efficient cure monitoring techniques. Cure monitoring will also allow

determine gelation time and vitrification (if any). The following of curing reaction is also important in order to optimize curing cycles and provide optimal mechanical properties.

Results of in-line measurements and calibration operations will be presented. This approach is useful during development (material and process parameters identification), as validation for simulation software, and directly in production in order to monitor and improve repeatability.

References

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